

Politecnico di Milano

SCHOOL OF INDUSTRIAL AND INFORMATION ENGINEERING

Master of Science – Energy Engineering

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Analysis and Optimization of a Domestic Hot Water Heat Pump Storage Tank

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Abstract

Domestic hot water production is one of the major causes of energy consumption in household. Different methods were developed during the years including heat pump systems.

The main drawback of heat pump application in the domestic hot water production is the low power available if compared to a boiler or to an electric water heater. For this reason, the heat pumps can't produce hot water instantaneously, then they need a storage tank in order to solve the mismatch between the domestic hot water demand and its production. Furthermore, thanks to this solution, the heat pump can work when the external conditions are favorable for its performance.

The storage tank must handle in the best possible way the incoming and outgoing water streams and the heat transfer from the condenser to the stored water. Since the storage contain water in a large temperature range, it should avoid strong mixing phenomena to maintain and high level of energy quality and to guarantee a certain volume of hot water always at the set-point temperature.

The main purpose of this work is to optimize the energy storage design for a domestic hot water heat pump system. Many studies were carried out on this topic, with several system configurations. In the case analyzed in this work, the condenser is an external source with very limited power, so the storage system designing can be different in respect of the standard solutions.

Chapter 1 presents a brief introduction on domestic hot water production, in term of energy consumption, market statistics and different production systems.

Chapter 2 introduces the functioning of the heat pump, their efficiency compared to other domestic hot water production systems, and the storage tank working conditions.

Chapter 3 presents and compare three different methods for studying the storage tank fluid dynamics.

Chapter 4 analyzes all the factors that influence the storage tank design. Several solutions are proposed and analyzed, through literature review, mathematical models, and CFD simulations.

Chapter 5 defines the conclusions of this work and proposes possibilities to further explore this study.

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